

Investigation on durability and fracture energy properties of geopolymers concrete with combined fine aggregates

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Geopolymer concrete (GPC) is an emerging technology which needs more attention in evolving sustainable construction industry. Further to avoid depletion of natural materials, utilising by products following waste management technologies is the need of the hour. River sand has become a scarce material today. On the other hand, Dredged Marine Sand (DMS) which faces the problem of disposal and acquiring large tracts of land, proves to be a substitute for river sand. In this paper, combination of M-sand and DMS was used in the place of river sand and fracture and durability aspects were investigated. The results indicate that GPC with DMS possesses very good fracture resistance characteristics as well as durability against acid and sulphate exposures and also have less pores and voids.

KEYWORDS: Geopolymer concrete; dredged marine sand (DMS); M-sand; fracture; ambient curing.

One of the major contributions of World's green house gas emission is Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC) production. In cement manufacture, CO₂ emission is by 54% of calcination and 46 % by burning of fuels¹. It is predicted that cement production may reach 4.8 billion tonnes in the year of 2050 due to 5% growth every year^{2,3}. As such, it is the need of the hour to go for alternative binding material. The emerging binding material which helps reducing CO₂ emission as well as the cost is the alumina silica based geopolymer. Materials rich in silica and alumina namely fly ash, GGBS, metakaolin, rice husk ash etc⁴ were used for making Geopolymer Concrete (GPC). Alumino silicate gel is formed due to the polymerization process by the presence of alumina and silica in the binder. Fly ash and GGBS have proved to be effective in the polymerization process⁵. Three types of curing, namely, heat curing, ambient curing and steam curing are currently in practice in case of GPC. Among these, ambient curing can be achieved with the help of utilizing GGBS along with fly ash. In

some studies, partial replacement by OPC is tried to enhance the curing regime⁶.

Durability is also an important aspect making geopolymer products viable in the construction field. Lot of studies have dealt with durability aspects like acid attack⁷, sulphate attack⁸, corrosion behavior⁹, water absorption, sorptivity etc. OPC gets degraded much by sulphate attack compared to GPC¹⁰⁻¹³. When concrete is exposed to acidic environment, diffusion reaction is caused due to the reaction of chemical constituents present in concrete¹⁴. GPC is formed by alumino silicate hydrate gel. As such, investigation of diffusion reaction is important in geopolymer concrete when fly ash and GGBS is used as binder. This paper reports different exposure conditions of GPC and the results obtained. Fly ash and GGBS is used as binder and combined fine aggregates (Manufactured Sand – M-sand and Dredged Marine Sand – DMS) in different proportions have been used. 70 percentage fly ash and 30 percentage GGBS is used as constant proportion